

Parental Pressure and Students Self-Efficacy

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Abstract: Parental Pressure is the drive that parents put on their children to achieve a goal. On one hand, student's self-efficacy is the belief of the students that they can do successfully a task whatever it is. Furthermore, this study used likert scale that was conducted among 245 students studying in Jagobiao National High School during September 2019. The result revealed that the parents hold high expectations from the students in terms of academic outcomes. While it was revealed also that the parents had a low attention in which they inconsistently go to school to check their children's school grades and performance. On the other hand, in terms of student's self-efficacy, they reported that they can always handle in solving difficult problems if they try hard enough. However, they do not have enough self-efficacy when it comes to dealing with unexpected events. In the findings of the study showed in Pearson Chi-square, it was presented that there is a significant association between the two variables parental pressure and students self-efficacy because the p value (i. e .000) is less than the alpha (i. e 0.05) the decision is reject H_0 and this means that parental pressure has to do with the students self-efficacy. It was also revealed that the student's self-efficacy is high when it comes in doing a task in school.

Keywords: Academic performance, Parental pressure, Self-efficacy, Students

I. INTRODUCTION

Parental Pressure is the state where parents drive their children to do well in many aspects. Sometimes parents force students to exceed in every endeavour especially in academic field. On one hand, self-efficacy is the belief that every individual have their own abilities, specifically the ability to meet the challenges ahead and complete a task successfully.

In a crucial manner, students who have experienced this kind of situation have the chance to excel academically as required of their parents. Students will do their best as their return of all the hard work and sacrifice of their parents. In Jagobiao National High School, there are students who are push by their parents to obtain high academic achievement. It makes them afraid and nervous if they fail to satisfy their parent's expectation from them especially when giving of report cards is near. Their parents might get mad on them if they do not pass their parents requirements such as attaining high grades and having academic achievements. Thus, the association between parental pressure and self-efficacy would give attainable heights of accomplishments of every student.

Parents forced their children to attain good performance in school [1]. However, students are obliged to do well in academic aspects as the requirement from their parents for various reasons particularly in social respect and parents' investment for their higher education [2]. However, students having a high level of self-efficacy have the belief that they are free and they control their own behaviors and life [3].

In the study, the researcher will gain knowledge on how strong or weak the correlation between parental pressure and student's self-efficacy in Jagobiao National High School. Through thus, the researcher will know if there is an association between the two variables.

The Problem

Furthermore, it seeks to answer the following:

1. What is the level of parental pressure felt by the students?
2. What is the level of self-efficacy of students in their studies?
3. Is there a correlation between parental pressure and self-efficacy of the students?

Theoretical Background

The study is supported by the Social Cognitive Learning Theory (SCLT) proposed by Albert Bandura. In his social cognitive learning theory, it is stated that people learn by watching others do, and how human thought process in understanding personality. In the context of this theory, self-efficacy was presented by Bandura that would serve as an exploratory model of how human behaves and its outcomes.

Furthermore, self-efficacy can be found at the center of SCLT and it means that the belief of a person that they can do a task to their ability and capacity. [4]. Individuals have beliefs in their own self-efficacy that influences whether or not they will reproduce an observed behavior. Recognizing the importance of reciprocal relationships that occurs between the behavior, the individual (cognitive), and the environmental influences in understanding how individuals learn [5]. Students learn from others by observing and imitating their behavior. In imitating another person, the student has to establish a commonality between the person's behavior and his/her own.

Students with high self-efficacy would probably get what they desired for. They would be able to perform a task efficiently with much self-confidence. Even their parents expect too much from them, they believe that they would meet their parents expectations. No matter how hard the situation is they will find a way to escape from it. Thus, the study concentrated in the association between parental pressure and student's self-efficacy.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Parents have too much anticipation from their children in academic performance [6]. Thus, parents' pressure towards their children is not so impending if they support them emotionally [7]. Parents who assist their children in terms of school activities, their children will excel in school [8]. Significantly, they have the chance in inspiring their children in terms of academic achievement [9]. Parental pressure is highly the reason why students experience academic stress [10]. Parents pressurized their children in order to attain desirable grades without thinking the abilities of their children [11]. Moreover, students have the fear of discouraging their parents in getting lower grades [12].

Some parents compared their children to the other people with high achievements [13]. Too much pressure coming from the parents to gain high achievement would result to anxiety [14]. It is suggested that the parents should know that the pressure they are injected to their children would lead to high anxiety and social isolation [15]. In the same manner, parents' pressure their children in academic activities creates stressful life of the students [16]. When the students feel high level of stress because of grades, they will hardly learn [17]. Consequently, they are obliged to do some preparations for their children in aiming academic success [18]. They are also the ones who instill good values to their children in preparation for school [19]. When the parents provided all the needs of their children, they will gain the full attention of their child when it comes to giving advices [20].

On one hand, student's personal drive and learning process can be identified through their level of self-efficacy [21]. During past two decades, self-efficacy is an effective predictor of student's motivation and learning [22]. Having a perceived self-efficacy will help humans to achieve success and it will help them personally in various ways [23]. Since the students have a high level of self-efficacy, they are more confident and have a majority of positive attitude toward their future career [24]. Student's self-efficacy plays an important role as predictors of academic achievement [25]. In any case, people who have high level of self-efficacy often feel that they have enough motivation that allow them to choose a tasks where they put effort unto it [26]. They are able to perform well, take part of activities and putting more effort in the challenging task to achieve the goal [27].

Students having a high level of self-efficacy have the belief that they are free and they control their own behaviors [28]. However, students with lower self-efficacy believed that intelligence do not have a role in improvement [29]. Students may boost their self-efficacy by listening to the experiences of the former student who have been successful [30]. Students who failed to do a task successfully, they believe that it is the product to a lack of effort [31]. The individuals in the immediate community of the students should strengthen the academic success of the students [32]. In connection, to those parents who actively join a program with their child has to do with the students' academic success in a manner that parents have the chance to reflect the previous performance of their child in the present [33]. Parents have an important role in encouraging their child to do so in every activity they are into [34]. Parent's desire towards their children has a significant input on student's belief that they can do a task on their own [35].

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Design

The study, Parental Pressure and Students Self-efficacy is a quantitative descriptive correlation that seeks the relation between parental pressure and student's self-efficacy. The data was gathered through the use of scoring instrument which helped the researcher in the data interpretation.

Locale

The study was held in Jagobiao National High School, a DepEd Managed Monograde Public Secondary School that fall under the 2nd District of Cebu, which located in Jagobiao, Mandaue City. It is known for its tidiness and good trainings for the students. Jagobiao National High School was one of the top finalist in the Ramon Aboitiz Foundation Inc. Seal of Excellence in Education in 2019 (RAFI SEED).

Population

The participants of the study consisted of all Senior High School Students. The grade 11 students with the solididity of 150 population, while grade 12 with the sum of 97 students. The definite number of Senior High School students was 245 from grade 11 to grade 12.

Instrument

The researcher used rating scale instrument for the collection of data. For part 1, the researcher made a univariate tool in which related to the level of parental pressure felt by the students that consisted of 10 indicators. For part 2, the researcher adapted a tool from an article by Schwarzer, R. and Jerusalem, M. the Generalized Self-Efficacy Scale that implied the level of student's self-efficacy consisting of 10 indicators. Both tools used Likert Scale in which the respondent's response based on a 4-point scale ranging from "Strongly Agree" (4) to "Strongly Disagree" (1). It used to measure the respondents concurrence with a variety of statements.

Data and Sources of Data

The researcher created a tool to collect data from respondents and their response was based on the rating scale instrument that was transmitted. The researcher asked permission from the school head, administrators, and the advisers in collecting data from respondents. When it was approved, the researcher explained the study to the respondents and its purpose in giving the survey questionnaire. Subsequently, the respondent's response were tabulated and analyzed by the researcher.

Statistical Treatment

In interpreting the data, the researcher used different statistical treatment. The average weighted mean and the chi-square. The average weighted mean will be used to determine the profile of the respondents. The chi-square helps the researcher to determine the association of the two variables parental pressure and student's self-efficacy.

Significance of the study

The result of this study would benefit the following individuals:

The students are the prior individuals that would benefit the study because by the end of this, they will gain some essential information about parental pressure and self-efficacy. They would determine if there is an association between the two variables.

The findings of the study will benefit the teachers as well in a matter that they would be able to guide the students and give them support on the things they think they can do.

The parents are the baseline of information towards their children. Knowing the result of the study, they would have the chance to loosen the pressure to their children and create another way to boost their children's self-efficacy.

The results will provide the community a significant knowledge especially to the parents on parental pressure and student's self-efficacy. It would serve as their guide in handling their children to attain good performance in school.

The researcher and future researcher will also benefit the said study which is "Parental Pressure and Students Self-Efficacy" because it could serve as their basis to their future studies.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. Parental Pressure

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Legend:
1. My parents push me to attain high grades.	2.62	Agree	1.00-1.75
2. My parents have high expectations from me.	2.91	Agree	(Strongly Disagree);
3. My parents compare my grades with my siblings.	2.61	Agree	1.76-2.50
4. My parents scold me when I get low grades.	2.45	Disagree	(Disagree);
5. My parents ask me about my test scores, homework's, etc.	2.53	Agree	2.51-3.25
6. My parents obliged me to have high achievements.	2.65	Agree	(Agree);
7. My parents always observed my school performance.	2.61	Agree	3.26-4.00
8. My parents supervised me when I do my assignments.	2.36	Disagree	(Strongly Agree)
9. My parents consistently go to school to check my school grades.	2.36	Disagree	
10. My parents get mad when I am excuse to my classes.	2.58	Agree	
Overall Weighted Mean	2.57	Agree	

e); 3.26-4.00 (Strongly Agree)

The table reveals the overall weighted mean was 2.57 and was interpreted as agree. In terms of the indicators, the statement "My parents have high expectations from me" had 2.91 and interpreted as agree. It indicates that the parents hold high expectation from the students. In the second to the highest weighted mean, the statement "My parents obliged me to have high achievements" had 2.65 and interpreted as agree. It signifies that parents constrain students to have high achievements. In the third to highest weighted mean, the statement "My parents push me to attain high grades" had 2.62 and interpreted as agree. It implies that parents push the students to obtain high grades.

On the contrary, the first to the lowest weighted mean had 2.45 and interpreted as disagree with the statement "My parents scold me when I get low grades". It indicates that only few of the students got scolded to their parents when they get low grades. The second to the lowest weighted mean had 2.36 and interpreted as disagree with the statement "My parents supervised me when I do my assignments". It signifies that not all of the parents look after the students when making their assignments. The third to the lowest weighted mean had 2.36 and interpreted as disagree with the statement "My parents consistently go to school to check my school grades". It implies that some parents inconsistently go to school to check the student's school grades. The study of [36] revealed that Asian and Latino students who experienced pressure to excel academically are because of the different parental expectations. Similarly, [37] study revealed that parental pressure is a good predictor for anxiety and not in stress matter among undergraduate business programmed students. However, the findings above did not support the findings of [38] if the parents monitor with the studies of their children it can improve their academic performance.

Legend: 1.00-1.75 (Strongly Disagree); 1.76-2.50 (Disagree); 2.51-3.25 (Agree); 3.26-4.00 (Strongly Agree)

Table 2. Students Self-Efficacy

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Legend:
1. I can always manage to solve difficult problems if I try hard enough.	3.16	Agree	1.00-1.75
2. If someone opposes me, I can find means and ways to get what I want.	2.89	Agree	(Strongly Disagree);
3. It is very easy for me to stick to my aims and accomplish my goals.	2.87	Agree	1.76-2.50
4. I am confident that I could deal efficiently with unexpected events.	2.73	Agree	(Disagree);
5. Thanks to my resourcefulness, I know how to handle unforeseen situations.	2.87	Agree	2.51-3.25
6. I can solve most problems if I invest the necessary effort.	3.08	Agree	(Agree);
7. I can remain calm when facing difficulties because I can rely on my coping abilities.	2.88	Agree	3.26-4.00
8. When I am confronted with a problem, I can usually find several solutions.	2.90	Agree	(Strongly Agree)
9. If I am in trouble, I can usually think of a solution.	3.01	Agree	
10. I can usually handle whatever comes my way.	2.98	Agree	
Overall Weighted Mean	2.94	Agree	

In terms of indicators, the statement "I can always manage to solve difficult problems if I try hard enough" had 3.16 and interpreted as agree. It indicates that students can always handle in resolving difficult problems if they try hard enough. In the second to the highest weighted mean, the statement "I can solve most problems if I invest the necessary effort" had 3.08 and interpreted as agree. It signifies that if the students invest requisite effort they can solve most problems. In the third to the highest weighted mean, the statement "If I am in trouble, I can usually think of a solution" had 3.01 and interpreted as agree. It implies that students can easily think of a solution if they are in trouble.

On the other hand, the first to the lowest weighted mean had 2.87 and interpreted as agree with the statement "It is very easy for me to stick to my aims and accomplish my goals". It indicates that not all of the students found easy in keeping their aims and goals. The

second to the lowest weighted mean had 2.87 and interpreted as agree with the statement “Thanks to my resourcefulness, I know how to handle unforeseen situations”. It signifies that few of the students can able to manage unexpected situations due to their resourcefulness. The third to the lowest weighted mean had 2.73 and interpreted as agree with the statement “I am confident that I could deal efficiently with unexpected events”. It implies that some of the students were confident in dealing with unexpected events. The study of [39] shows that the majority of the respondents have the belief that they can do all of the school activities positively that will improve their academic performance. The findings of [40] support the study above that self-efficacy belief have been found to be sensitive to subtle changes in student’s performance context, learning processes and students academic achievement. [41] Study shows that interviewee’s responses showed that students with high self-efficacy planned to study complex subjects in future.

Table 3. Parental Pressure & Students Self-Efficacy

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	6.789E2 ^a	532	.000
Likelihood Ratio	436.545	532	.999
Linear-by-Linear Association	6.212	1	.013
N of Valid Cases	245		

580 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .01.

There is a significant association between the two variables parental pressure and student’s self-efficacy because $0.000 > 0.05$. The decision is to reject H_0 and this means that parental pressure has contributed to the students self-efficacy in terms of academic achievement. The study of [42] presents parental involvement in education did not significantly influence student’s academic performance. Consequently, the findings did not support the findings of [43] that the parent pressure affects positively on students academic achievement in school. Results of the study conducted by [44] found out that there is positive and significant association between academic self-efficacy of the students and their academic performance.

In this study, the researcher found out that the students have high level of parental pressure such as parents have high expectations to their students. Also, parents obliged students to have high achievements and they push them in attaining high grades. On the other hand, students have high level of self-efficacy beliefs such as students can always manage in solving difficult problems if they try hard. Also, they can solve problems if they invest necessary efforts and if they are in trouble they can usually think of solutions.

In this study, it implies that the students have a high self-efficacy in doing various tasks given to them. They believed that whatever the task is, they will be able to do it successfully. Parent’s pressure towards their children to attain good performance is high as well. This means that the parental pressure towards their children is an effective strategy in boosting the self-efficacy of the study. Having a high self-efficacy would help the students to achieve a goal. It will boost their self-confidence in many aspects. It has proven to be responsive to improvements in student’s methods of learning. But too much pressure from the parents would lead to stressful life of the student’s worst, it might lead to depression. Parents must observe their children’s capacity and capability first than expecting too much from their children to attain high academic performance. It was revealed that there is a significant association between the two variables parental pressure and student’s self-efficacy.

Recommendations

The various recommendations were as follows:

1. It is recommended that the students must boost their self-efficacy so that they can attain good performance in school.
2. The parents must continue in monitoring their children in order to achieve what they want from their children.

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